

The Sanctuary of Pasikrata at Demetrias

By Stelios Ieremias, Independent researcher

Entry tags: Religious Complex, Religious Place, Greek Religions, Greek Cult, Thessalian Religions, Graeco-Roman, Aegean, Religious Group, Thessaly, Greece, Hellenistic Religions, Macedonian Religions

During excavations of the city walls and the south cemetery by A.S. Arvanitopoulos from 1912 to 1915, several sanctuary deposits were revealed just outside a gate of the wall of Demetrias in the southern cemetery. The deposits yielded a wealth of finds: a life-size marble head, marble statuettes (some of which depict Artemis and Aphrodite), inscribed votive stelai and incense burners (miniature altars) mentioning Pasikrata and Artemis En(n)odia, clay vases and lamps, a large clay bust, numerous terracotta figurines, depicting women, men, and children, among which a significant number of kausia boy figurines. In the past, Nikolaos Papachatzis had interpreted the deity as "Aphrodite of the Dead". However, Maria Stamatopoulou's research on the excavation archives and the re-evaluation of the finds has argued that the worshipped deity(-ies) had a kourotrophic nature, protecting life passages of children and women.

Date Range: 294 BCE - 200 CE

Region: The Sanctuary of Pasikrata.

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Balkans, Thessaly

The sanctuary was located just outside a gate of the walls of Demetrias and next to the southern cemetery. Since A.S. Arvanitopoulos' excavations in the early 20th century it has not been possible to precisely locate the site, thus the area on the map is only approximate.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Arvanitopoulos, A.S. 1928. *Γραπτά Στήλαι Δημητριάδος-Παγασών*. Athens: 45.
- Source 2: Papachatzis, N. N.K. 1958. "Η Πασικράτα της Δημητριάδας". *Thessalika A*: 50–65.
- Source 3: Stamatopoulou, M. 2014. "The Pasikrata Sanctuary at Demetrias and the Alleged Funerary Sanctuaries of Thessaly: a re-appraisal." *Kernos* 27: 207–55.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://journals.openedition.org/kernos/2281>

– Source 1 Description: Article by Maria Stamatopoulou on the sanctuary, its finds and their interpretation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Even though A.S. Arvanitopoulos' excavation journals of the sanctuary remain lost, we know from other sites he excavated that he did keep stratigraphy (which was not always common for the time), and the most valuable tool for the identification of the old finds are his finds photographs which document a great number of them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1912-1915

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Demetrias - Sanctuary of Pasikrata

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Unclear

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary is located just outside the ancient city walls.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary was located near a road leading outside of the city and next to the south cemetery.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Although the sanctuary is not inside the city's habitation fabric, it is not far away.

Specific to this answer:

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

A single structure

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Arvanitopoulos mentioned that he did not find any buildings belonging to a sanctuary, but as Maria Stamatopoulou suggested, it is possible that he might have confused the sanctuary structures and identified them as funerary, due to the proximity to the cemetery and the graves.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

One single feature

– Other [specify]: Unclear

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

A group of structures:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: Several sanctuary deposit pits were discovered, some shallow and some deep, containing the dedications.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

|

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The inscriptions mention the deities Pasikrata and Artemis En(n)odia.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Based on the number of inscriptions that mention Pasikrata, it seems that she was the main venerated deity, and Artemis En(n)odia was a second deity that was worshipped. Statuettes and figurines of Aphrodite also exist, although a few, and she is not mentioned in inscriptions. A Nike terracotta figurine also exists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Based on our current knowledge, it is not clear how the sanctuary was founded.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: Although inscribed monuments have been discovered, based on the other finds as well, the sanctuary did not house sacred texts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not certain if and how many structures existed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what structures existed and whether any of them were monumental.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: The goddess Pasikrata has been interpreted as a kourotrophic deity, protecting worshippers through important life stages and passages.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No such evidence exists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A female, life-size, marble head exists among the finds, but it is not certain whether this belongs to the cult statue.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though the worshippers venerated Pasikrata, there is no evidence for communication with the goddess.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Arvanitopoulos does not mention any sacrifice remains, but this should not necessarily exclude the possibility.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: There are several marble dedications.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

Notes: Exception to this are the few clay vessels which survive, that could have been used in daily-life as well. However, it is not certain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: The pits which contained the votives have been interpreted as part of a cleaning operation at the sanctuary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: It is most likely a local cult, furthermore the inscriptions seem to be dedicated by inhabitants of Demetrias.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear. Clay vessels have been found, but it is not certain if they would have been used in feasting, or if they were only dedications.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Based on the current knowledge, it is unclear, but not unlikely.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The discovery of clay lamps and incense burners indicate some form of ritual taking place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: An inscription mentions that a certain Theano completed her service as priestess to Pasikrata.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

↳ Present part time
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Demetrias

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Yes
Notes: The one inscription which mentions a priestess, seems to point to females.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Demetrias

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Demetrias

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Demetrias

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– No
Notes: Theano's inscription marks the end of her service, thus this points that the priesthood was not for life.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Demetrias

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Demetrias

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Demetrias

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Apostolos Arvanitopoulos S.. Γ Αρχαιολογική Περιφέρεια. Περί των εν τω ιερῷ της Πασικράτας και παρακείμενω αρχαίω Νεκροταφείω εν Δημητριάδι.

Reference: Apostolos Arvanitopoulos S.. Ανασκαφαί και Έρευναι εν Θεσσαλία και Μακεδονία κατά το Έτος 1912.

Reference: Sofia Kravaritou. Sacred Space and the Politics of Multiculturalism in Demetrias (Thessaly). (Milena Melfi , Olympia Bobou), Hellenistic Sanctuaries. Between Greece and Rome. Oxford University Press. isbn: 9780199654130.

Reference: Stelios Ieremias. The Hellenistic Terracottas from Demetrias (unpublished DPhil thesis). University of Oxford.

Reference: Nikolaos Papachatzis K.. Η Πασικράτα της Δημητριάδας.

Reference: Stelios Ieremias. The Kausia boy figurines from Demetrias: a reassessment. doi: 10.1017/S0068245421000046.

Reference: Apostolos Arvanitopoulos S.. Γραπταί Στήλαι Δημητριάδος-Παγασών.

Reference: Maria Stamatopoulou. Demetrias: The Archaeology of a Cosmopolitan Macedonian Harbour. (Myrina Kalaitzi , Paschalis Paschidis , Claudia Antonetti , Anne-Marie Guimier-Sorbets undefined), Βορειοελλαδικά. Tales from the Lands of the Ethne. Essays in Honour of Miltiades B. Hatzopoulos. National Hellenic Research Foundation, Institute of Historical Research. isbn: 9789609538718.

Reference: Maria Mili. Religion and Society in Ancient Thessaly. Oxford University Press.

Reference: Sofia Kravaritou. Synoecism and religious interface in Demetrias (Thessaly). Kernos, 24(1) issn: 2034-7871. doi: 10.4000/kernos.1942.

Reference: Maria Stamatopoulou. The Pasikrata Sanctuary at Demetrias and the alleged funerary sanctuaries of Thessaly: a re-appraisal. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4000/kernos.2281>.